

Research and Applications

Qualitative analysis of the participation of three vocational students in a STEM project

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Awareness of the scientific process is a fundamental skill for citizens living in a society shaped by science and technology. However, science does not always reach all students, either through formal or non-formal science education. In this study, we analysed the participation of three vocational students (aged 17-19 years) in a multimedia course, who embarked on a guided project. The students captured and analysed images of solar phenomena and produced a video illustrating dynamic processes on the Sun's surface, which they presented at the European Researchers' Night (NEI). Following the event, a semi-structured interview was conducted with the students involved to evaluate their satisfaction with participating and the significance they attribute to space exploration. The results indicate that the project motivated the students by engaging their multimedia skills in a scientific context and also sparked interest in Astronomy-related content.

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1. Introduction

Since the early telescopic era, records of sunspots have shown that changes on the Sun's surface have long inspired careful observation ([Carrasco et al., 2022](#)). Although sunspots were first observed thousands of years ago (e.g., [Persson, 2013](#); [Lorensi & Pacini, 2016](#)), Galileo's observations in 1612 proved that the Sun rotates by tracking sunspots (e.g., [Zhou, 2023](#)). Solar eruptions and coronal mass ejections (CMEs) release charged particles that can interfere with satellites (e.g., [Shrivastava et al., 2020](#)), causing disruptions across various social and economic sectors (e.g., [Cliver et al., 2022](#); [Gafeira et al., 2023](#)).

[Arsioli & Orlando \(2024\)](#) report recent findings showing unexpected gamma-ray emissions that challenge current models and open new questions in high-energy astrophysics. Research in solar astrophysics can benefit from the application of AI algorithms, which reveal patterns and features often overlooked by classical techniques long-used to interpret solar observations, such as spectral line fitting or time-series analysis (e.g., [Asensio Ramos et al., 2023](#)). Scientific literacy must evolve alongside technological

change by promoting citizens' awareness of the environmental, social, economic and political dimensions of the Earth system's challenges, enabling them to participate actively and responsibly in society (e.g., [Ribeiro & Vasconcelos, 2024](#)). On the other hand, scientific research also depends on public interest, as funding often comes from public support (e.g., [Ehrenfreund et al., 2010](#)). Research suggests that daytime solar observation provides practical opportunities to explore key astronomy concepts (e.g., [Costa & Maroja, 2017](#); [Fonte et al., 2025](#)) and helps promote scientific literacy through different learning experiences ([Anjos & Carvalho, 2020](#)).

2. Problem

Many students develop a negative attitude toward science as they progress in their studies, driven by fear of failure, pressure to maintain high grades, and lack of support—leading them to choose subjects where they believe they have a better chance of academic success (e.g., [Gopal, 2025](#)). Based on a study conducted with students from four European countries, [Bekaert et al. \(2022\)](#) found that they often apply solar concepts incorrectly. [Cyparsade & Adiapen \(2012\)](#) address the low scientific literacy among students in vocational courses, evidenced by initial difficulties in understanding astronomical concepts. Moreover, many students show significant gaps in scientific literacy, particularly in astronomy ([Turmambekov et al., 2025](#)). According to these authors, low astronomical literacy has fostered the spread of pseudoscientific beliefs, exacerbated by limited coverage in mandatory physics courses that fail to promote a systematic understanding.

Despite its importance, the Sun's impact on climate and its dynamic processes is still not fully understood (e.g., [Rosenberg et al., 2013](#)), making continued research vital for developing technology and mitigating hazards. Furthermore, the increasing complexity of solar phenomena and their relevance to modern society — from space weather forecasting (e.g., [Temmer, 2021](#)) to the protection of sensitive technologies (e.g., [Gafeira et al., 2023](#)) — reinforce the need to promote greater awareness and understanding of the Sun and solar phenomena among all population segments, including those not typically engaged with the physical or astronomical sciences. It is crucial to question whether young people understand the Sun's role in sustaining life and to assess the impact of their participation in scientific projects (e.g., [Montalvan Castilla, 2025](#)). Thus, this study aims to analyse how participation in a STEM project contextualised in solar physics promotes the development of positive attitudes toward astronomy. This, together with critical thinking and civic skills, is essential for today's society ([Perea et al., 2021](#)).

3. Methodology

This study analysed the impact of STEM projects on three vocational students who participated in a scientific outreach initiative. It involves understanding the Sun's dynamics

and recognising its essential importance to life on Earth.

To assess students' knowledge of the Sun's characteristics and the surface's energetic phenomena, a baseline questionnaire was administered prior to the Solar observation project (see [Appendix A](#)). The first part of the questionnaire contains three multiple-choice and two true-or-false questions. In the second part, respondents identify which of the six solar energetic phenomena they had previously heard of.

For the solar project, the participants developed an activity that they presented at the European Researchers' Night (NEI). Following the NEI outreach event, individual semi-structured interviews (see [Appendix B](#)) were conducted with the three students involved in the project to provide a holistic view of the case. The main goal was to analyse their attitudes towards science, their awareness of the Sun's importance, and their understanding of the scientific process after their participation.

A qualitative approach using thematic analysis was applied to identify patterns in interviews, reflections, and interactions ([Nowell et al., 2017](#)). This method allows the identification of recurring themes in engagement, collaboration, and learning, offering deep insight into students' experiences in STEM education ([Tang et al., 2024](#)). In this way, we can delve into students' lived experiences, highlighting not only what students do, but also how and why they engage in specific ways within STEM activities ([Mateos-Núñez et al., 2020](#)). This qualitative method is particularly valuable for small sample sizes, as they offer a rich, contextualised understanding of individual and group participation (e.g., [Kiger & Varpio, 2020](#); [Lochmiller, 2021](#)).

4. Characterisation of the study group

The study group consisted of three students from the multimedia design vocational course (designated P1, P2, and P3) at a Portuguese school. They had previously created a video for the inauguration ceremony of an astronomical space at their school, and they were invited to collaborate on the solar project because of their multimedia skills.

The study group's responses to questions 1-5 of the questionnaire are presented in [Table 1](#). We found that the vocational students had some knowledge about the Sun's surface temperature but were more uncertain about other aspects. For example, two believed the Sun is larger than any visible star. Regarding energy production, they attributed it either to surface combustion or merely to the Sun's natural brightness. Only one student recognised the existence of solar rotation. Overall, their prior knowledge was generally low, with all three students having only heard of solar spots, but none demonstrated a deeper understanding of solar structure, physical processes, or energy production. Based on these answers, we conclude that the students in the study group lacked in-depth knowledge of solar phenomena. Through informal conversations with them, we found out that they were not particularly motivated or interested in astronomy

prior to participating in the project. Their project participation was related to their multimedia coursework rather than a pre-existing interest in science. According to [Sensoy & Varzikioglu \(2025\)](#), participation in structured scientific activities in astronomy simultaneously enhances students' academic performance and their curiosity about the subject. These authors show that such activities and games boost motivation, promote active participation, and increase students' interest and creativity in astronomy.

Student	1	2	3	4	5
P1	✓	✓	On its burning surface.	✓	False
P2	It is larger than any star visible in the night sky.	✓	Nowhere, it just has a natural glow.	... it has no atmosphere.	✓
P3	It is larger than any star visible in the night sky.	✓	✓	✓	False

Table 1 Study group's responses to questions 1-5 of the questionnaire

5. The project

The Solar Project combined direct solar observation with science communication, aiming to build both technical and scientific skills. That encompasses two complementary dimensions: (1) it focuses on developing research skills and scientific knowledge, leading to the production of a final product; (2) it examines participants' engagement throughout the process, the dissemination of their work, and their perception of space sciences. It is worth emphasising that for [Ribeiro & Vasconcelos \(2024\)](#), non-formal activities complement curricula, addressing relevant but under-represented topics that will enhance students' understandings.

The Solar Project was presented at the NEI, an annual European event designed to spark young people's interest in science and highlight the impact of researchers on daily life. The event also promotes the participation of students who are not motivated to engage with science, bringing them closer to the scientific community. The project consisted of recording one-minute videos at hourly intervals over the two days of the course, as shown in [Table 2](#). [Figure 1](#) presents images of the students documenting their observations during this period. In the end, using

the images they had obtained and edited, they produced a video¹ about the Sun.

Day	Start time of the approximately 1-minute videos									
3/9/2024	9:00	9:49	10:50	11:50	12:54	13:51	14:53	15:44	16:46	17:49
4/9/2024	8:50	9:51	10:48	11:56	12:57	13:52	14:48	15:44	16:47	17:48

Table 2 Student-recorded hours of sunspot footage.

Figure 1 Images captured during the observation sessions listed in [Table 2](#)

During the project, the students used the skills they had developed throughout their vocational course to create the video. All three collaborated in data collection, telescope setup, and image capture. Each participant had a specific role in the project: P1 was responsible for aligning the solar equator with the horizontal axis in Photoshop, P2 created the video introduction and the closing credits, and P3 recorded the video narration.

6. Results

According to the preliminary questionnaire, the students in the study group were unfamiliar with solar phenomena, except for the existence of sunspots and the Sun’s high surface temperature. What we found by interviewing these students is that participation in the project

opened a new world for them as they made their first observations.

The analysis of the interviews revealed that:

P1 was pleased with the experience of processing images and interacting with the public. They expressed an increased interest in astronomy, particularly highlighting their new-found understanding of sunspots as a key point. They also mentioned that they developed new skills in using image editing software, particularly Photoshop. During the interview, P1 emphasised the importance of space exploration for understanding Earth's future, the conditions on other planets, and humanity's role in the cosmos.

P2 shared their experience, stating that they initially had little interest in astronomy but came to appreciate it through the project. P2 emphasised the importance of understanding scientific methods and the relevance of space exploration, stressing that such research could help detect hazardous meteors and reveal new insights about other planets. P2 also argued that, despite Earth's existing problems, investment in space exploration remains vital, as it can bring benefits for our planet. They concluded by pointing out that many materials and technologies in use today have their origins in space research, underscoring its positive impact on humanity.

P3 stated that they learned new facts about telescopes and the Sun, which boosted their interest in astronomy. They indicated that participating in the project enhanced their awareness of scientific processes and reinforced the importance of space exploration. P3 argued that expanding space knowledge could help humanity find alternative habitats if Earth became uninhabitable. Additionally, P3 highlighted the significant benefits of space exploration, such as the development of new technologies and tools that enhance our ability to observe and study the Universe.

7. Discussion of results and conclusions

Based on the students' observations made during the project, and the interviews conducted with them at its conclusion, several insights can be drawn:

- a) All three students highlighted their overall satisfaction and appreciated the opportunity to apply their existing multimedia skills in a new context.
- b) The students reported an interest in astronomy, though they did not specify the reasons for this change beyond recognising that their knowledge had grown.
- c) Regarding understanding of science and its methods, only one student reported deeper knowledge of the Sun, while the others did not indicate any significant improvement.
- d) All students stressed the importance of investing in space exploration, linking it to the idea that, in the event of a major disaster, humanity might one day need to relocate to another

planet.

e) This idea of preparing for a possible escape from Earth came up when the students were asked to weigh the balance between investing in solving Earth's problems and exploring space.

f) Regarding the benefits of space exploration, the students primarily highlighted the generation of knowledge, both as a means to develop new materials and as a valuable goal in itself.

As demonstrated here, the students appear motivated by applying their multimedia expertise in the Solar Project. They also credit astronomy and space exploration as potential areas for investment, indicating interest in astronomy-related content. However, the interviews revealed the same limited ideas: that space exploration is primarily a means of escaping the Earth, overlooking or lacking awareness of its broader objectives. From our perspective, this shows that the students do not truly understand space exploration. In this sense, we believe the intervention was not as successful as expected in improving scientific learning.

This short exploration shows that interdisciplinary projects that promote the use of specific skills in new contexts can be an effective strategy to increase motivation and interest in science. However, this study focuses only on three students of multimedia course. We believe that a larger study with more diverse participants could yield more data to inform our conclusions and verify whether these results can be replicated in other contexts.

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Notes

1. NEI 2024: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qyTtKNez_So

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Appendix

Appendix A: Questionnaire

About the size of the Sun. (Select one)

- It is larger than any star visible in the night sky.
- It is the size of the Earth.
- It is the size of the Moon.
- It is the size of an ordinary star, with a radius more than 100 times greater than that of the Earth.

The average surface temperature of the Sun is about... (Select one)

- 250 °C (Temperature inside an oven).
- 1500 °C (Melting point of Iron).
- 3000 °C (Boiling point of Iron).
- 6000 °C (higher than the temperature inside the Earth).

Where is the Sun's energy obtained? (Select one)

- On its burning surface.
- Inside, where there is oil.
- In the core, where nuclear reactions occur.
- Nowhere, it just has a natural glow.

The Sun ... (Select one)

- ... has no atmosphere.
- ... has an atmosphere with different layers.

The Sun has a rotation movement. (Select one)

- True
- False

Which of the following phenomena occurring on the Sun have you heard of? (Select all that apply)

- Sunspots
- Flares
- Prominences
- Granulation
- Solar Wind
- Matter ejections
- None

Appendix B: Interview

What did you enjoy the most while carrying out the project?

Do you think that by participating in this project you developed or increased your interest in astronomy?

And what skills do you think you acquired regarding the understanding of science and scientific methods by taking part in this project?

Do you think it is relevant to invest in space exploration or do you think we should not be spending so much money on space exploration?

With so many problems on Earth, why invest in space?

Do you think that space exploration has always been beneficial for humanity, and why? If you think it has or has not been beneficial, why do you hold that opinion?